

**NEW TEST METHOD AND MONITORING TECHNIQUE
TO EVALUATE MODE III AND
MIXED MODE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

A new test method to evaluate Mode III fracture toughness, and a novel technique to accurately determine the onset of delamination of Mixed Mode Edge Delamination Test (EDT) coupons, of both thermosetting and thermoplastic composite materials, has been developed. Mode III fracture toughness is determined by using a Double Split Double Cantilever Beam (DSDCB). In addition, a simple fixture is used to provide a Mode III fracture toughness expression inherently independent of the crack length. As a result, the value of the fracture toughness depends on the geometry and the applied load, which are constant during crack propagation. Theoretical formulation as well as experimental results for thermosetting and thermoplastic materials are discussed. The novel technique to determine the onset of delamination of EDT coupons is based on monitoring the changes in the Poisson's ratio of the specimen rather than the conventional longitudinal strain. The Poisson's ratio is monitored by simultaneously recording the longitudinal and transverse strain at the "to be delaminated" edges. A 3-D finite element analysis of the tested coupon was conducted to confirm the location of the strain gages. Experimental values of various thermosetting and thermoplastic composites, and the different mechanisms of delamination propagation, are presented.

KEYWORDS: Mode III; Mixed Mode, Delamination; Fracture; Toughness, Interlaminar.

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination, or interlaminar cracking, is considered to be one of the predominant types of damage in composite materials. The initiation and growth of delamination may result in progressive stiffness degradation, reduction in load-carrying capacity, and eventual failure of composite structures. Interlaminar crack propagation can occur under opening, shearing, tearing, or a combination thereof; hence, it is of practical interest to characterize the onset of this interlaminar cracking.

Most of the work to date has focused on Mode I and to a lesser extent on Mode II, and the mixed I and II Modes. The most commonly used specimens for Mode I characterization are the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen [1] and the width-tapered double cantilever beam (WTDCB) [2,3]. Recently, a height-tapered double cantilever beam (HTDCB) was introduced [4] to study rate effects on delamination fracture toughness.

Mode II fracture toughness is usually evaluated by using the end notch flexure (ENF) specimen. Crack lap shear (CLS), mixed mode flexure (MMF) specimens [5], and Arcan fixture [6] are methods used to evaluate fracture toughness of various ratios of Modes I and II. The edge delamination test (EDT) coupon is the most commonly used configuration to evaluate mixed mode fracture toughness [7,8]. The conventional experimental method employs a longitudinal strain gage or extensometer to detect the onset of delamination. Since the onset of delamination is a highly localized phenomenon initiated at the edges of the coupon, in many cases it will not be reflected immediately and/or significantly on the overall longitudinal stress strain curve. One of the objectives of this work is to develop a measurement technique to accurately detect the onset of delamination in EDT coupons.

Little work has been performed on the measurement of Mode III (tearing mode) fracture toughness of composites. Donaldson [9] described a split DCB specimen made by bonding the composite laminate between two aluminum bars. These bars were then loaded in the direction parallel to the crack plane and normal to the beam length. As in the case of Mode I DCB, the load drops suddenly as the crack extends, causing some uncertainty in the crack length corresponding to the critical load. This results in relatively high scatter of the experimental data. Becht and Gillespie proposed a crack rail shear specimen for Mode III characterization [10]. They showed analytically that this specimen may give good results provided some simplifying assumptions are met, such as uniform crack extension along the entire specimen length.

Depending on loading conditions and part geometry, Mode III fracture toughness may play an important role in damage accumulation and failure of composites. The main objective of this work was to develop a specimen geometry and an experimental procedure for accurate determination of Mode III fracture toughness of unidirectional composites.

2. DETERMINATION OF MODE III FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

2.1 Specimen Geometry A double split double cantilever beam (DSDCB) is shown in Fig. 1. The symmetry of the specimen ensures self balancing and prevents twisting of the specimen when loaded. The strain energy stored in a single beam under a tearing load P is:

$$U = \frac{P^2 L^3}{6EI} \quad (1)$$

where P = applied load
 L = beam (crack) length
 E = longitudinal modulus
 I = moment of inertia of the beam cross section.

The energy release rate of a single split DCB with respect to crack propagation is:

$$G = \frac{1}{h} \frac{dU}{dL}$$

or

$$G = \frac{P^2 L^2}{EIh} \quad (2)$$

where h is the thickness of the specimen.

FIGURE 1. Geometry of Double-Split Double Cantilever Beam (DSDCB) specimen

Common problems encountered with most DCB specimens are the unstable propagation of the crack, and the correlation of the load with the corresponding crack length. In a deflection-controlled tearing, as the crack propagates, the compliance changes and the load drops. The load will increase as the beam is elastically deflected until the critical load is reached (lower than the previous critical load) and the crack propagates again. The inaccuracy in identifying and measuring the correct crack length and the corresponding critical load, which are required to calculate the energy release rate, G , complicates and reduces the reliability of this method.

The stick-slip phenomenon associated with the specimen illustrated in Fig. 1 can be eliminated by adding a support to the DSDCB, as shown in Fig. 2. The strain energy for a supported beam will be given by the following expression:

$$U = \frac{P^2 e^3}{6EI} \left(1 + \frac{3a}{4e} \right) \quad (3)$$

where e = distance from loading end to support
 a = distance from support to crack tip.

Here, the total crack length is $L = e + a$.

FIGURE 2. Loading condition of a DSDCB specimen with intermediate support

The advantage of this specimen configuration becomes evident when deriving the critical energy release rate for the specimen:

$$G_{III} = \frac{P^2 e^2}{4EIh} \quad (4)$$

The above expression for Mode III fracture toughness is inherently independent of the crack length. Hence, for a specimen with constant geometry and mechanical properties, the critical tearing load, P , should remain constant as the crack propagates.

2.2 Experimental Procedure

- 2.2.1 Specimen Configuration** Two toughened thermosetting and three thermoplastic composite material systems were used to fabricate the coupons for the Mode III fracture toughness tests as indicated in Table 1. The geometry of the test specimen is a DSDCB as shown in Fig. 1. Two cuts are splitting the edge into three beams of 25 percent, 50 percent, and 25 percent of the 100-mm (4-in.) width of the specimen. The cuts were machined to a length of 38 mm (1.5 in.) and then the cracks were initiated by an additional 6.5 mm (0.25 in.) to provide sharp edges.

TABLE 1. MODE III FRACTURE TOUGHNESS FOR VARIOUS MATERIAL SYSTEMS

Material System	Type of Resin	Fracture Toughness, G_{III} kJ/m ²
IM7/977	Thermoset	2.6
IM6/8552	Thermoset	2.4
IM7/APC-2	Thermoplastic	3.8
IM6/AVIMID-K	Thermoplastic	3.1
KEVLAR/J2	Thermoplastic	2.9

- 2.2.2 The Testing System** A fixture was built to support the coupon during the test. Two sets of adjustable rollers provide the mid-point simple support required to generate a constant critical load as described earlier (Fig. 3). The force splitting the specimen was applied through flexible cables attached to a set of edge clamps that provided free rotation as the beams deflected (Fig. 4). One cable was pulled over a pulley fixed to the stationary top grip. This configuration provided an equal deflection for both sides of the stationary coupon.

FIGURE 3. Loading fixture for DSDCB specimen

FIGURE 4. Intermediate support and end clamping of the DSDCB specimen

The test fixture with the coupon was affixed to the 8502 servo-hydraulic Instron dynamic testing machine. Load and deflection data were recorded continuously by a computer, and stored for further manipulations.

2.3 Results and Discussion The objective of the present work was a proof of concept rather than a parametric study. Therefore, only a few parameters affecting the propagation of the Mode III cracks were investigated.

The data recorded during the load deflection tests were plotted to calculate the average critical load. In most cases a 15-point average procedure was employed to "filter out" the noise due to the relatively low load level (Fig. 5). Fig. 5 shows a load-deflection curve of a Kevlar[®]/J2 coupon. The intermediate support was positioned 25 mm (1.0 in.) from the loaded edge. The first part of this curve, up to 4 mm (0.15 in.) of deflection, corresponds to the elastic deflection of the beams. Thereafter, the deflection increases at a constant load due to the propagation of the cracks. Superimposing the load deflection curves of two Kevlar/J2 coupons of the same geometry (Fig. 6) illustrates the good correlation and the repeatability of the technique.

FIGURE 5. Effect of noise filtering on load-deflection curve of a DSDCB specimen

FIGURE 6. Load-deflection curves of two Kevlar/J2 DSDCB specimens

The load deflection behavior of the Kevlar/J2 coupons shown in Fig. 6 demonstrates a smooth transition between the elastic deflection and the crack propagation portions of the curve. This smooth transition is attributable to the crack initiation of the preliminary cuts prior to the fracture test. The effect of not initiating the cuts is shown in Fig. 7. Two IM7/977 unidirectional coupons were tested at different support distance e . Both curves demonstrated a high overshoot of the critical load as the cracks started to propagate through the blunted fronts of the cuts. The effect of different support distance on the critical load is also evident from this figure.

FIGURE 7. Effect of intermediate support distance on the critical load in a DSDCB test

Fiber bridging phenomenon was not significant in most cases. The effect of fiber bridging in this type of apparatus depends mainly on fiber alignment of the unidirectional coupons. Fig. 8 shows a significant effect of fiber bridging of an IM6/8552 coupon. The fluctuation in the critical loads were caused by the fibers peeling off and bridging from one side of the shearing (tearing) crack to the other and eventually breaking.

FIGURE 8. Effect of fiber bridging in a DSDCB test

A summary of G_{III} results for all tested composite material systems is shown in Table 1. As expected, the fracture toughness values of the thermoplastic materials was higher than those of the thermosetting composites. Donaldson [9] reported a Mode III fracture toughness of about 2 kJ/m² for AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy composite. Since the thermosetting composites tested in the present work are with toughened epoxies, the higher values shown in Table 2 are reasonable.

The main advantage of this G_{III} test method is in its simplicity. However, it is sensitive to fiber alignment, coupon thickness, and amount of deflection. As mentioned above, fiber misalignment will be reflected in fiber bridging associated with a higher fluctuating critical load, i.e., fracture toughness. The thickness appears in the fracture toughness equation with a power of four. Small errors in measurements, or nonuniformity in the coupon thickness, will have a significant effect when the thickness is small, e.g., less than 2 mm (.080 in.). In addition, a thicker coupon will demonstrate smaller deflection, which will minimize the axial component of the reaction at the intermediate support.

3. MONITORING THE ONSET OF DELAMINATION OF EDT COUPONS

3.1 Measurement Technique Concept In most experimental methods the value of the longitudinal strain, at the onset of delamination, is used directly to calculate the interlaminar fracture toughness of the tested coupon. It is therefore of practical interest to obtain that critical strain as accurately as possible. The conventional experimental method employs a longitudinal strain gage or extensometer to detect the onset of delamination by examining the changes in the longitudinal stress-strain behavior. Since the onset of delamination is a highly localized phenomenon, initiated at the edges of the coupons, in many cases it will not be reflected immediately and/or significantly on the overall longitudinal stress-strain curve.

The layout of edge delamination test (EDT) coupons is usually [+35/-35/0/90]_S. This layout is designed to maximize the difference between the Poisson's ratio of various layers and thus maximize the interlaminar stresses. This situation is also required to minimize the chances that the tested coupon will fail in tension before delamination occurs. Typical Poisson ratio values of the [+35/-35/0] and the [90] layers are 1.00 and .02, respectively. The delamination in this case will develop at the interface between the 0- and 90-degree layers.

The new technique monitors the onset of delamination by measuring the changes in the Poisson's ratio of the "to be delaminated" area. This is accomplished by measuring the transverse and the longitudinal strains simultaneously. The transverse strain changes would be much more sensitive to the delamination, and the corresponding longitudinal strain can be evaluated more accurately.

3.2 Experimental Procedure

3.2.1 Specimen Configuration Edge delamination test coupons were loaded in tension to generate delamination for the evaluation of the interlaminar fracture toughness, G_C , using unnotched [+35/-35/0/90]_S, the geometry of which is shown in Fig. 9. Two miniature gages (0.031 in.) were transversely attached along the edges of the coupon on opposite faces, in addition to a conventional longitudinal extensometer. The size of the transverse gages was selected to measure the localized effect of the onset of delamination. The gages were mounted midway between the tabs of the coupon to maximize the probability of picking up the changes in transverse strain right above the initiation of delamination, as will be explained later.

FIGURE 9. Geometry and strain gage arrangement of edge delamination test (EDT) coupon

The fracture toughness of six composite material systems was evaluated in this study - two thermoplastic, three toughened thermoset, and one standard graphite/epoxy thermoset composite. These material systems are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2. MIXED MODE FRACTURE TOUGHNESS FOR VARIOUS COMPOSITE MATERIAL SYSTEMS.

Material System	Resin Type	Mode III Fracture Toughness, G_c kJ/m ²
IM6/3501-6	Standard Thermoset	0.17
IM7/977	Toughened Thermoset	0.35
Celion 6K/R6376	"-	0.32
IM6/8552	"-	0.23
IM7/APC-2	Thermoplastic	1.05
IM6/AVIMID-K	"-	0.39

The coupons were loaded in tension using the 8502 servo-hydraulic Instron Dynamic Testing Machine. The load, the longitudinal, and the transverse strains were recorded simultaneously by a computer and stored for further processing.

3.2.2 Finite Element Method Verification of Gage Location The delamination initiates as a result of the development of high interlaminar stresses arising due to the high Poisson's ratio mismatch between the 90-degree layer and the rest of the coupon. When the coupon is loaded in tension, the transverse displacement in the area adjacent to the tabs is restricted and thus the difference between the Poisson's ratios is suppressed. Therefore, the farther the location from the tabs, the higher the difference

between the Poisson's ratios. Hence, it is reasonable to assume that the probability of delamination initiation at the mid-point between the tabs is highest.

Three-dimensional finite element analysis was conducted to determine the distribution of all six stress components. It was found that all interlaminar stresses at the interface between the 0-degree and the 90-degree layers show a clear maximum at the edges mid-way between the tabs. A typical result of the interlaminar stresses is shown in Fig. 10.

3.3 Results and Discussion Mixed Mode fracture toughness of EDT coupons was calculated by loading the coupons in tension and measuring the longitudinal strain at the onset of delamination. This value was substituted into the fracture toughness expression:

$$(G_c)_i = \left[\frac{(\epsilon_c)_i^2 t}{2} (E_{lam} - E^*) \right]_i \quad (5)$$

where

- ϵ_c = longitudinal strain at the onset of delamination
- i = index of tested coupon
- t = thickness of coupon
- E_{lam} = stiffness of coupon as calculated from Classical Lamination Plates (CLP) theory
- E^* = reduced stiffness given by:

$$E^* = \frac{1}{8} (6E_{[+35/-35/0]_s} + 2E_{[90]}) \quad (6)$$

where

- $E_{[90]}$ = stiffness of the 90 layer
- $E_{[+35/-35/0]_s}$ = stiffness of the $[+35/-35/0]_s$ as calculated from CLP.

The Mixed Mode final value was calculated by averaging all test coupon results for the same material system.

In all tested coupons the delamination was initiated at or near the mid-point of the side surface. The delamination was initiated at one of the 0/90 interfaces, and thereafter fluctuated between the two 0/90 interfaces.

Thermoset composite coupons demonstrated three stages of failure process - delamination initiation, propagation, and final failure. The changes in the transverse strains at the delamination area were, as expected, about 8 to 15 times higher than the changes in the longitudinal strain, as shown in a typical result on Fig. 11a and 11b, respectively. Plotting Poisson's ratio curve, the onset of delamination with the associated critical longitudinal strain can be clearly observed (Fig. 11c). This is shown as the sharp turning point where the Poisson's ratio increases from about 0.3 to an artificial value of 3 to 10 due to rapid propagation of the delamination. As the delamination propagates farther away from the location of the transverse strain gage location, the Poisson's ratio decreases and approaches the value of the $[+35/-35/0]$ layer.

The results for the thermoplastic composite coupons were quite different. Due to the coupon's high fracture toughness, delamination did not propagate as rapidly as with the thermoset composites. Moreover, in some cases, the final failure was very close to the onset of delamination so that no apparent effects of the delamination could have been found on the traditional longitudinal stress-strain curve, as shown typically on Fig. 12.

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FIGURE 10. Interlaminar normal and shear stress distribution at the 0/90 interface of an EDT coupon under prescribed tensile strain of 1 percent

Edge Delamination - IM7/977

(a)

Edge Delamination - IM7/977

(b)

Edge Delamination - IM7/977

(c)

FIGURE 11. Typical mixed mode fracture toughness test results for a [+35/-35/0/90]_s thermoset EDT coupon. a. Stress-longitudinal strain curve. b. Stress-transverse strain curve. c. Poisson's ratio curve.

Edge Delamination - IM6/AVIMID-K

(a)

Edge Delamination - IM6/AVIMID-K

(b)

Edge Delamination - IM6/AVIMID-K

(c)

FIGURE 12. Typical mixed mode fracture toughness test results for a [+35/-35/0/90]_s thermoplastic EDT coupon. a. Stress-longitudinal strain curve. b. Stress-transverse strain curve. c. Poisson's ratio curve.

The experimental results of the calculated interlaminar fracture toughness, G_c , are given in Table 2.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A method to determine the fracture toughness in tearing mode (Mode III) and a measuring technique to determine the onset of delamination of EDT coupons were evaluated for thermosetting and thermoplastic composite materials. Based on the experimental examination of the two methods, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The Double Split Double Cantilever Beam (DSDCB) configuration is an efficient, easy-to-use tool to determine the Mode III fracture toughness of unidirectional composite laminates. For small deflections, the critical load remains constant during crack propagation.
2. The thickness of the DSDCB coupons should not be less than 2 mm (0.080 in.) to minimize sensitivity to thickness nonuniformity and decrease the deflection to reduce the axial component of the reaction at the intermediate support.
3. Monitoring changes in Poisson's ratio of edge delamination test (EDT) coupons in Mixed Mode interlaminar fracture toughness can provide an accurate determination of the onset of delamination. This method is about 10 times more sensitive than the traditional monitoring of the longitudinal strain.

5. REFERENCES

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